

Even-odd Harmonious Labeling of Some Graphs

Dhvanik Zala, Narendra Chotaliya, Mehul Chaurasiya

Abstract: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph, with $m = |V(G)|$ and $n = |E(G)|$. An injective mapping $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2m - 1\}$ is called an even-odd harmonious labeling of the graph G , if $\exists$ an induced edge mapping $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 2, 4, \dots, 2(n - 1)\}$ such that (i) f^* is bijective mapping (ii) $f^*(e = pq) = (f(p) + f(q)) \pmod{2n}$. The graph acquired from this labeling is called even-odd harmonious graph. In this paper, we discovered some interesting results like H-graph, comb graph, bistar graph and $\langle k_{1,n}^{(1)}, k_{1,n}^{(2)}, k_{1,n}^{(3)} \rangle$ graph for even-odd harmonious labeling.

Keywords: Comb graph, Even-odd harmonious labeling, H-graph, Injective mapping

I. INTRODUCTION

Graph labeling is an engrossing and sizable research in the arena of graph theory. It trades in how vertices and edges of a graph are labelled corresponding to certain mathematical condition[1]. From Galian[5], the neoteric research development in the sphere of graph labeling is taken. The pioneer of graph labeling was A. Rosa[10]. Books of Harary[2] and D.B.west[8] are being used for the ideas and basic knowledge. The harmonious graph have instigated [3] in 1980. Z.liang etl[8] set forth the odd harmonious graphs in 2009 and in 2011 P.B.sarasijia etal [10] investigated the even harmonious graphs. Further Adalin Beatress and Sarasijia in [2] set forth the even odd harmonious graphs. We have manifested distinct graphs, as we have collected distinct types of graphs in forms of even - odd harmonious labeling.

II. BASIC TERMINOLOGY

Definition(16) 2.1: A graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$ with n edges is called a harmonious, if there is an injective function $f: V(G) \rightarrow Z_n$ such that when each edge uv is allotted the label $\{f(u) + f(v)\} \pmod{n}$, the resulting edge labels are different. When the graph G is tree, exactly one edge label may be used on two vertices.

Definition(17) 2.2: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph, with $m = |V(G)|$ and $n = |E(G)|$. $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2m - 1\}$ is said to be an even-odd harmonious labeling of the graph G if $\exists$ an induced edge mapping $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 2, 4, \dots, 2(n - 1)\}$ such that (i) f^* is bijective mapping (ii) $f^*(e = pq) = (f(p) + f(q)) \pmod{2n}$. The graph acquired from this labeling is called even-odd harmonious

graph.

Definition(18) 2.3: The H-graph of a path P_m is the graph secured from two copies of path P_m with vertices $u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_m$ and $v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_m$ by attaching the vertices $\frac{u_{m+1}}{2}$ and $\frac{v_{m+1}}{2}$ if m is odd and the vertices $\frac{u_{m+1}}{2}$ and $\frac{v_m}{2}$ if m is even.

Definition(18) 2.4: A comb graph is a graph obtained by attaching a single pendent edge to each vertex of a path. The comb graph is defined as $P_m \odot K_1$. Where $P_m = \{v_1, \dots, v_m\}$ be the path with m vertices which contains $2m$ vertices and $2m - 1$ edges.

Definition(19) 2.5: The bistar graph $B_{m,n}$ is a graph acquired from a path P_2 by attaching the root of stars S_m and S_n at the terminal vertices of P_2 , the bistar graph is denoted by $B_{m,n}$.

Remark: In this paper, we use "EOHL" instead of "even-odd harmonious labeling", for the simplicity.

III. EVEN-ODD HARMONIOUS LABELING OF ACYCLIC GRAPH

Theorem 3.1: The H-graph of path P_n is an even-odd harmonious graph.

Proof: Let $G = H_n$ be the H-graph. Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ be the vertices of graph G and

$$E(H_n) = \{u_i u_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1} \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1\} \cup \left\{ \frac{u_{n+1}}{2} \mid n \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \right\} \cup \left\{ \frac{u_{n+1}}{2}, \frac{v_n}{2} \mid n \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \right\}$$

Note that, $p = |V(G)| = 2n$ and $q = |E(G)| = 2n - 1$. Define an injective function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 4n - 1\}$ such that

Case-1: - When $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} i & ; i \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ 2n + i - 1 & ; i \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases} \quad \text{and}$$

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 3n + i - 1 & ; i \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ n + i & ; i \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

Case-2: - When $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} i & ; i \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ 2n + i - 1 & ; i \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases} \quad \text{and}$$

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 2n - i & ; i \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ 4n - i + 1 & ; i \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

and an induced edge function $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 2, 4, \dots, 4n - 4\}$ such that

Case-1: - When $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$

$$f^*(e_i) = f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = (2n + 2i) \pmod{2q}, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$$

$$f^*(e_j) = f^*(v_j v_{j+1}) = 2(2n + i) \pmod{2q}, 1 \leq j \leq n - 1$$

and

$$f^*(e') = f^*\left(\frac{u_{n+1} v_n}{2}\right) = (2q + 2) \pmod{2q}.$$

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Case-2: - When $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$

$$f^*(e_i) = f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = (2n + 2i) \pmod{2q}, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$$

$$f^*(e_j) = f^*(v_j v_{j+1}) = (5n - 2(i - 1) + 4) \pmod{2q},$$

$$1 \leq j \leq n - 1 \text{ and}$$

$$f^*(e') = f^*\left(u_{\frac{n}{2}+1} v_{\frac{n}{2}}\right) = (2q + 2) \pmod{2q}.$$

The above labeling pattern give rise EOHL to the graph G , as f is an injective mapping and f^* is one-one and onto. Thus, the H -graph is even-odd harmonious graph.

Fig.1 EOHL of H_6

Fig.2 EOHL of H_7

Theorem 3.2: The comb graph C_{bn} is an even-odd harmonious graph, when $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$.

Proof: Let $G = C_{bn}$ be a comb graph, where $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ be the vertices of the graph G .

$$E(G) = \{u_i v_i \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\} \cup \{u_i u_{i+1} \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1\}.$$

Here, $p = |V(G)| = 2n$ and $q = |E(G)| = 2n - 1$.

Define an injective function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 4n - 1\}$ by

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} i & ; i \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ n + i & ; i \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases} \text{ and}$$

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 3n + i - 1 & ; i \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ 2n + i - 1 & ; i \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

and the corresponding induced edge function

$$f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 2, 4, \dots, 4n - 4\}$$

$$f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = (n + 2i + 1) \pmod{2q}, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$$

$$f^*(u_i v_i) = (5n + 2i - 1) \pmod{2q}, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$$

therefore, the function f^* is bijective. Thus, the graph

$G = C_{bn}$ ($n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$) admits an EOHL and hence it is an even-odd harmonious graph.

Fig.3 EOHL of comb graph C_{b7}

Theorem 3.3: The bistar graph $B_{m,n}$ is an even-odd harmonious graph.

Proof: Let $G = B_{m,n}$ be a bistar graph.

We know that, in bistar graph, $p = |V(G)| = m + n + 2$ and $q = |E(G)| = m + n + 1$. Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ be the vertices of the graph G .

Also,

$$E(G) = \{u u_i \mid 1 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{u v\} \cup \{v v_j \mid 1 \leq j \leq n\}.$$

Now, an injective function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2m + 2n - 3\}$ is defined as follows:

$$f(u) = 1, \quad f(v) = 2p - 1$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq m$$

$$f(v_j) = 2m + 2j + 1, 1 \leq j \leq n$$

and the corresponding edge labeling function

$f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 2, 4, \dots, 2m + 2n\}$ is defined as follows:

$$f^*(e) = f^*(u v) = 2q + 2 \pmod{2q}$$

$$f^*(e_i) = f^*(u u_i) = 2(i + 1) \pmod{2q}, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$$

$$f^*(e_j) = f^*(v v_j) = m + n + 2j \pmod{2q}, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

The above labeling pattern give rise EOHL to the graph $B_{m,n}$, as f is an injective mapping and f^* is one-one and onto function. Thus, the bistar graph $B_{m,n}$ is an even-odd harmonious graph.

Fig.4 EOHL of the bistar graph $B_{5,3}$

Theorem 3.4: The graph $\langle k_{1,n}^{(1)}, k_{1,n}^{(2)}, k_{1,n}^{(3)} \rangle$ is an even odd harmonious graph.

Proof: Let $G = \langle k_{1,n}^{(1)}, k_{1,n}^{(2)}, k_{1,n}^{(3)} \rangle$. Let u_i be the apex vertex of $k_{1,n}^{(i)}$; $1 \leq i \leq 3$ and $v_1^{(i)}, v_2^{(i)}, \dots, v_n^{(i)}$ be the pendent vertices of $k_{1,n}^{(i)}$ for $1 \leq i \leq 3$.

Here, apex vertices u_1 and u_2 are adjacent to the vertex w_1 , u_1 and u_2 are adjacent to the vertex w_2 .

So $p = |V(G)| = 3n + 5$ and $q = |E(G)| = 3n + 4$

Define an injective function

$f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 3(2n + 3)\}$ such that

$$f(u_i) = 2i - 1; i = 1, 2, 3$$

$$f(w_i) = 2i + 2^i n + 5; i = 1, 2$$

$$f(v_j^{(i)}) = (2i + 3) + 2n(i - 2) + 2j; j = 1, 2, \dots, n; i = 1, 2, 3$$

and the corresponding edge labeling function is defined as follows:

$$f^*(u_i w_j) = 2j + 5 + 2^j n + (2i - 1) \pmod{2q}; \text{ where } 1 \leq i \leq 3, j = 1, 2$$

$$1 \leq i \leq 3, j = 1, 2$$

$$f^*(u_i v_j^{(i)}) = 2(2i + 1) + 2n(i - 2) + 2j \pmod{2q}; \text{ where } 1 \leq i \leq 3, 1 \leq j \leq n$$

$$1 \leq i \leq 3, 1 \leq j \leq n$$

Hence f^* is bijective. Thus, the graph

$G = \langle k_{1,n}^{(1)}, k_{1,n}^{(2)}, k_{1,n}^{(3)} \rangle$ admits an EOHL, hence the graph $\langle k_{1,n}^{(1)}, k_{1,n}^{(2)}, k_{1,n}^{(3)} \rangle$ is an even odd harmonious graph.

Fig.5 EOHL of $\langle k_{1,6}^{(1)}, k_{1,6}^{(2)}, k_{1,6}^{(3)} \rangle$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we investigated some bunch of graphs of acyclic graphs such as H-graph, comb graph, bistar graph and the graph $\langle k_{1,n}^{(1)}, k_{1,n}^{(2)}, k_{1,n}^{(3)} \rangle$ which all are even-odd harmonious labeling. Also, we have proved that, comb graph C_{bn} is an even-odd harmonious graph, when n is even.

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